

EFFECTS OF THE LEARN TO READ PROGRAM TO THE GRADE III PUPILS OF SAN JUAN UNIT 1 ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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Effects of the LEARN TO READ Program to the Grade III Pupils of San Juan Unit 1 Elementary School

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Abstract

Reading is an essential skill integral to daily life, facilitating interactions with texts ranging from street signs to personal messages. The inability to read limits access to information and opportunities, underscoring the importance of effective literacy programs. This study evaluated the impact of the "LEARN TO READ" program on 20 Grade III pupils, including 11 non-readers and nine pupils at the frustration reading level. In the pre-test, all participants scored at the BEGINNING level. After implementing the intervention, the post-test results showed significant improvements: students could produce letter sounds, read consonant-vowel (CV) blends, and read consonant-vowel-consonant (CVC) words spontaneously, achieving the ADVANCED level. Statistical analysis revealed a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores, demonstrating the program's success in advancing pupils from non-reading or frustration levels to proficient CVC word readers. Based on these findings, it is recommended that the remediation program be continued into the next grade, focusing on advancing skills to reading phrases, sentences, and simple stories with comprehension. Additionally, the "LEARN TO READ" program is recommended for broader adoption among educators working with non-readers and frustration-level pupils to enhance literacy outcomes in English classes.

Keywords: *LEARN TO READ Program, reading, literacy program*

Introduction

Reading is a very important skill. The ability to read and understand what one reads will open up an exciting new world. Reading is a part of life for it is involved in almost all human activities: reading signs and directions on streets and buildings; distinguishing one food label from another; reading announcements; reading messages from loved ones and friends; reading and laughing from funny comic strips; and many more. One's life would be bleak if he doesn't know how to read (Gonzales, 1992). According to Elizabeth Hardwick, the greatest gift is a passion for reading, for it gives the reader knowledge of the world and a wide range of experiences.

As embodied in the DepEd Memoranda no. 324 s. 2004 and no. 345 s. 2010, one of the main thrusts of the 2002 Basic Education Curriculum is to ensure that every child is a successful reader at the end of Grade III. DepEd enforces the "Every Child a Reader Program", thus, the Bureau of Elementary Education developed the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI).

In the mid-year assessment of Phil-IRI last October 2016, it was found out that there were 11 non-readers and 9 frustration-level pupils in English out of 198 Grade III pupils of San Juan Unit-1 Elementary School. To address the problem, the school head came up with Project RSI (Reading Support Initiation). The objective of the project was to help non-readers and frustrated-level pupils learn to read in English. The employed reading teacher developed a reading remediation program called LEARN TO READ with the hope that this would be the answer to the problem of the existence of non-readers, which she also experienced in her own class.

The purpose of this action research was to know the effects of the said reading remediation program.

Research Questions

This study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of reading skill of the Grade III pupils before and after the intervention in terms of:
 - 1.1. letter-sound correspondence;
 - 1.2. CV letter combination; and
 - 1.3. CVC word recognition?
2. Is there a significant difference on the reading skills of the Grade III pupils before and after the intervention in terms of:
 - 2.1. letter-sound correspondence;
 - 2.2. CV letter combination; and
 - 2.3. CVC word recognition?

Methodology

The study was experimental research. The single group with a pre-test and a post-test design was used in the study. The subject of the study was the 11 non-readers and the 9 frustration-level pupils in Grade III of San Juan Unit-1 Elementary School. To determine the level of reading skill of the Grade III pupils, pre-test was given. Post-test was given after 55 days of teaching following the lessons in the reading remediation program. In the pre-test, a teacher-made assessment tool was used. In the post-test another teacher-made assessment tool was used with the same characteristics as that of the assessment tool used in the pre-test. The pre-test and post-test

were given through oral assessment. Mean was used in the computation. Numerical weights were assigned to the different levels of reading skill which is shown below.

- 9-10 (A) Advance
- 7-8 (P) Proficient
- 5-6 (AP) Approaching Proficiency
- 3-4 (D) Developing
- 0-2 (B) Beginning

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Level of Reading Skill of the Grade III Pupils Before and After the reading Remediation Program*

Level of Reading Skill	Pre-test		Post-test	
	Average	Level	Average	Level
A. Letter-Sound correspondence	2.50	Beginning	9.70	Advance
B. CV letter combination	1.95	Beginning	9.20	Advance
C. CVC word recognition	0	Beginning	9.10	Advance

It can be gleaned from the table that in the pre-test, the Grade III pupils got an average of 2.50 in the reading skill letter-sound correspondence, which is within the level BEGINNING, while in the post-test, they got an average of 9.7, which is within the level ADVANCE. In the pre-test, the Grade III pupils got an average of 1.95 in CV letter combination, which is within the level BEGINNING, while in the post-test, they got an average of 9.2, which is within the level ADVANCE.

In the reading skill CVC word recognition, the Grade III pupils got an average of 0 in the pre-test, while in the post-test, they got an average of 9.1, which is within the level ADVANCE. To determine the difference between the computed mean of the pre-test and the post-test as to the levels of reading ability of the Grade III pupils, namely letter-sound correspondence, CV letter combination, and CVC word recognition, a t-test was used.

Table 2. *Dependent T-test Result Comparing the Mean of the Pre-test and the Post-test*

Factors	Mean		df	t-tabulated	t-computed	Verbal Interpretation
	Before	After				
Letter-sound correspondence	2.50	9.70	19	2.093	11.05	Significant
CV letter combination	1.95	9.20	19	2.093	12.13	Significant
CVC word recognition	0	9.10	19	2.093	24.18	Significant

It can be seen from the table that there was an increase in the post-test of all the levels of reading skill namely letter-sound correspondence from 2.50 to 9.70; CV letter combination from 1.95 to 9.20; and CVC word recognition from 0 to 9.10. The computed value of all the levels of reading skill was higher than the critical value. Therefore, there was a significant difference in the results of the pre-test and the post-test.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research conducted, the following conclusions were drawn: In the pre-test, the 11 non-readers and nine frustration-level pupils in Grade III belong to the BEGINNING level. In the post-test, the pupils were able to produce letter sounds, read CV blend, and read CVC words spontaneously. The pupils are now CVC word readers, they are in the ADVANCE LEVEL. There was a significant difference in the results of the pre-test and the post-test. Therefore, the LEARN TO READ program was successful in making the 11 non-readers, and nine frustration-level pupils in Grade I learn to read CVC words in English.

In the light of the findings of this research, the Reading teacher/researcher recommends the following: It is highly recommended that the reading remediation program for this group of children at risk be continued to the next grade level, targeting the next reading skills, reading phrases, sentences, and simple stories with comprehension. It is highly recommended that the reading remediation program LEARN TO READ be used by other teachers who have non-readers and frustration-level pupils in English in their classes.

Action Plan

Objectives, Activities, Time Frame and the Persons Involved in the Plan of Action

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Activities	Time Frame	Persons Involved
1. Results of the Action Research	1. Discuss the results to the school head and master teachers in the school.	-meeting with the school head and master teachers	- June-March	-Teacher researcher, school head, master teacher

	2.	Present the results of the action research to the faculty of San Juan Unit-I Elementary School	-meeting with the faculty of San Juan Unit-I Elementary School	- June- March	-Teacher / researcher teachers of SJU-I ES
2.	Using / Adopting the LEARN TO READ program (For Teacher Development)	1.	Impart the importance and the benefits of the LEARN TO READ Program to the teachers of SJU-I ES in teaching reading or providing reading remediation to their pupils	-LAC Sessions - School visits in other districts and other divisions if possible	- June- March -Teacher / researcher, teachers of SJU-I ES -Teacher / researcher, school heads of other schools
	2.	Impart the importance and the benefits of the LEARN TO READ Program to other teachers in other districts and in other divisions if possible			

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